

Preparation and Spectral Studies of some Carboxyalkyl Substituted Thioureas as Potential Fungicides and Nematicides

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A survey of literature reveals that some work has been reported on thioureas and substituted thioureas¹, but not much work has been done on the preparation and spectral studies of carboxyalkyl substituted thioureas. The present communication reports the preparation, characteristics and screening of these compounds against two fungi *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Pythium aphanidermatum* and two nematodes *Meloidogyne javanica* and *Anguina tritici*.

- 1, R₁=H, R₂=C₂H₅
- 2, R₁=H, R₂=CH₂C₆H₅
- 3; R₁=H, R₂=*p*-CH₃C₆H₄
- 4, R₁=CH₃, R₂=C₂H₅
- 5, R₁=CH₃, R₂=CH₂C₆H₅
- 6; R₁=CH₃, R₂=*p*-CH₃C₆H₄
- 7; R₁=CH₂C₆H₅, R₂=C₂H₅
- 8; R₁=R₂=CH₂C₆H₅
- 9; R₁=CH₂C₆H₅, R₂=*p*-CH₃C₆H₄
- 10, R₁=CH(OH)CH₃, R₂=C₂H₅
- 11; R₁=CH(OH)CH₃, R₂=CH₂C₆H₅
- 12; R₁=CH(OH)CH₃, R₂=*p*-CH₃C₆H₄
- 13, R₁=CH₂COOH, R₂=C₂H₅
- 14; R₁=CH₂COOH, R₂=CH₂C₆H₅
- 15, R₁=CH₂COOH, R₂=*p*-CH₃C₆H₄

Experimental

The chemicals used were of G.R. (E. Merck or Sarabhai M) grade. Ethyl, benzyl and *p*-tolyl isothiocyanates were prepared by the reported method².

Fifteen carboxyalkyl thioureas were prepared as follows. To a solution of amino acids (glycine, alanine, β-phenyl alanine, threonine and aspartic acid; 0.05 mol) in minimum amount of 1 N NaOH, was added an equivalent amount of the isothiocyanates (ethyl, benzyl and *p*-tolyl) solution in minimum amount of ethanol. The mixture was stirred for 48 h at room temperature, then cooled in an ice-bath, acidified with 1 : 1 HCl and filtered. The resulting solid was washed with cold water and crystallised from ethanol/acetone. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc, elemental analysis for N and S and molecular weight deter-

mination by cryoscopic method. M.ps. were determined by a Genson apparatus. Electronic spectra (EtOH) were determined on a Beckman DU-20 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (nujol or KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 237B spectrophotometer and the nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian A-60 D/Perkin-Elmer R-32 instrument using TMS as internal standard.

The compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against *R. solani* and *P. aphanidermatum* by poisoned food technique³ at four different concentrations, viz. 100, 50, 10 and 1 ppm, and EC_{50} was calculated by using log-probit scale. The compounds were also screened for their nematocidal activity⁴ against *M. javanica* and *A. tritici* at three dilutions, viz. 1 : 5, 1 : 10 and 1 : 20.

Results and Discussion

The ir spectra showed bands at 3 150–3 400 (OH+NH), 1 510–1 540 and 1 405–1 430 (NH+NCN+C=S), 1 205–1 290 (C=S+NCN+C-OH), 1 005–1 095 (NCN+C=S+C=N), 705–795 (NH+C=S+NCS) and 605–690 cm^{-1} (C=S+CH) suggesting the most probable structures for these substituted thioureas⁵. All the carboxyalkyl thioureas exhibited three intense bands at 202–210, 231–241 and 262–272 nm. In compounds 10–12, these peaks were observed at 212–216, 271–276 and 311–317 nm, corresponding to high energy $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of C=O group⁶, thiocarbonyl $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of C=O group respectively. The nmr spectra of compounds 1, 4, 9, 10 and 14 (one from each series) were taken as representative case : 1, m.p. 170°, δ 1.15–1.40 (3H, t, *J* 8 Hz, CH_3), 3.87 (2H, s, CH_2 -R), 4.25 (2H, s, CH_2COOH) and 8.65–8.90 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 2 \times NH); 2, m.p. 160°; 3, m.p. 185°; 4, m.p. 100°, δ 1.15–1.45 (3H, t, *J* 8 Hz, CH_3), 1.55–1.85 (3H, t, *J* 10 Hz, CH_3CHCOOH), 3.75–4.15 (2H, d, *J* 7 Hz, CH_2) and 8.80–9.00 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 2 \times NH); 5, m.p. 140°; 6, m.p. 158°; 7, m.p. 215°; 8, m.p. 208°; 9, m.p. 165°, δ 2.30–2.50 (3H, t, *J* 8 Hz, CH_3), 3.30 (1H, s, CHCOOH), 4.73 (2H, s, CH_2Ar), 6.75–7.00 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, ArH, *ortho* to NH), 7.15–7.40 (5H, m, ArH) and 7.55 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, ArH, *meta* to NH); 10, m.p. 104°, δ 0.95–1.10 (3H, t, *J* 8 Hz, CH_3), 1.15–1.45 (3H, t, *J* 8 Hz, CH_3CHOH), 1.98–2.15 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, CH_2), 2.32 (1H, s, CH), 4.02 (1H, s, CHCOOH) and 6.32 (1H, s, OH); 11, m.p. 108°; 12, m.p. 213°; 13, m.p. 240°; 14, m.p. 215°, δ 3.05 (2H, s, CH_2COOH), 5.07 (2H, s, CH_2Ar) and 7.25–7.55 (5H, m, ArH); 15, m.p. 153°.

Biological activities : The toxicity data (EC_{50} $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) reveal that compounds 2 (0.42), 4 (1.01), 5 (0.76), 8 (0.36), 10 (0.83), 11 (1.00) and 15 (0.10) were highly toxic against *R. solani* and compounds 1 (0.49), 5 (0.47), 7 (0.29), 9 (1.00), 12 (0.40), 13 (0.13) and 15 (0.32) were highly toxic against *P. aphanidermatum*. Compounds 1 (85.7) and 8 (94.9) were found to be highly effective against *M. javanica*

having more than 75% mortality. Compounds 5 (63.6), 3 (63.0), 12 (60.4), 4 (58.7) and 1 (52.0) were effective against *A. tritici* having more than 50% mortality; values in the parenthesis are the average of per cent mortality at the three stated dilutions.

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